
DRS Utilities Guide

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**Program for Climate Model Diagnosis and Intercomparison
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Browsing DRS files: DRSED

1.1 Concepts

DRSED is a utility program for interactively browsing DRS files. DRSED can:

- list the variables in a DRS file,
- print a full description of a variable,
- modify the variable description,
- print a portion of a variable, and
- write a portion of a variable or variables to an ASCII output file.

1.1.1 Notation

The following notation is used throughout this document for specifying syntax:

- [] (square brackets) denote optional tokens;
- | denotes ‘or’;
- ... (ellipsis) denotes a sequence;
- == denotes ‘is defined as’.

1.1.2 Variables

A DRS *variable* is an array of up to four dimensions. A variable may be floating-point, integer, or character string valued. Conceptually, DRS file consists of a set of variables. The **list** command prints the names and titles of all variables in a file.

Table 1 lists the descriptive information which DRS keeps for each variable.

TABLE 1Variable descriptive information

Field	Description	Max characters
name	Short identifier	16
source	Comments	120
title	Long identifier	80
units	Units description	40
time	Timestamp	16
type	Data type.	8

The descriptive information about a variable may be viewed with the **describe**, **name**, **source**, **title**, **units**, **time**, and **type** commands.

Table 2 lists the descriptive fields kept for each dimension of a variable.

TABLE 2Dimension descriptive information

Field	Description	Max Characters
name	Short identifier	16
units	Units description	40
source	(unevenly-spaced dimensions only) Comments	120
title	(unevenly-spaced dimensions only) Long identifier	80

Dimension information can be printed with the **describe**, **name**, **source**, **units**, and **title** commands.

Table 3 lists the datatypes supported by DRS.

TABLE 3DRS datatypes

Datatype	Description
I*4	Integer, 32-bit 2's complement
I*8	Integer, 64-bit 2's complement
C*n	Character string, n bytes per string
R*4	Floating-point, IEEE 32-bit
R*8	Floating-point, Cray 64-bit

The type of a variable may be determined using the **type** or **describe** commands.

1.1.3 Current variable

During an interactive session, DRSED remembers the name of the variable most recently accessed. If the variable name is omitted from a command, the current variable is assumed.

1.1.4 Current file

At most one DRS file can be open at a given time. If a new DRS file is opened via the **open** command, the previous file is automatically closed. Similarly, at any time there may be at most one ASCII output file open.

1.1.5 Range specifications

The **print**, **printi**, and **length** commands require range specifications of the portion of the variable to be accessed. The form of a range specification is

$$name(\textit{dimension-range}_1, \dots, \textit{dimension-range}_n)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \textit{dimension-range} == \\ \textit{dimension-value} \mid \textit{dimension-value}_1 : \textit{dimension-value}_n \mid * \end{aligned}$$

For the **print** command, the *dimension-value* is an actual value of the dimension. If a single dimension value is specified, DRSED prints the variable value corresponding to that dimension value. If a range of values is specified with the *value* : *value* notation, DRSED prints the variable values corresponding to the range of dimension values bracketed by *dimension-value*₁ and *dimension-value*_n. A dimension range of '*' indicates all values of the dimension. The order of the dimension ranges corresponds to the order in the file, as indicated by the **describe** command.

For the **printi** command, a dimension value is an integer index, with index 1 being the first dimension value, in the order indicated by the describe command.

For example, if variable hflxsen is defined on a longitude-latitude-time grid, with longitude varying from 0.0 to 358.125, latitude from 90.0 to -90.0, and time from 0.0 to 10.0 in increments of 1.0, then

```
print hflxsen(*,90.0,0:5)
```

prints the values of hflxsen corresponding to all longitude values, latitude -90.0, at times 0 to 5. The equivalent **printi** command would be

```
printi hflxsen(*,1,1:6)
```

1.1.6 Missing data

The DRS missing data flag for floating-point data is a value of 1.0 E20. DRS prints such a value as a dash ('-').

1.2 Running DRSED

The command syntax for DRSED is:

```
% drsed [DRS-dictionary-file]
```

where *DRS-dictionary-file* is the file name of a DRS .dic file. The ‘.dic’ filetype may be omitted. If no file is specified on the command line, a file may be opened within DRSED via the **open** command.

On the PCMDI cirrus machine, DRSED is located in directory

```
/usr/local/PCMDI/bin
```

To run DRSED, the environment LD_LIBRARY_PATH must contain the directory containing the Fortran libraries. Typically this is in /usr/lang/SCx.0, where x is some numeral specifying the current Fortran version. For example, in the .login file:

```
setenv LD_LIBRARY_PATH /usr/lang/SC1.0: etc.
```

1.3 Commands

Table 4 lists the DRSED commands.

TABLE 4

DRSED commands

Command	Functionality
close	Close the current ASCII output file.
create <i>outputfile</i>	Create an ASCII output file. If any ASCII output file is currently open, it is closed first.
describe [<i>variable</i>]	Print a complete variable description.
help [<i>command</i> all]	Print help text. If no command is specified, a short description of all commands is given.
length [<i>variable</i>][<i>(user-dimension-ranges)</i>]	Print the number of elements in the variable.
list [brief full]	Print a variable list. A full list (the default) gives the title of each variable with its name. A brief list gives names only.
mode [interactive batch]	Set interaction mode (default is interactive).
name [<i>dimension-number</i>] [<i>variable</i>]	Print the name of a variable (if no dimension-number is specified) or dimension of a variable. The dimension number, if specified, is an integer from 1 to 4.
nd [<i>variable</i>]	Print the number of dimensions of a variable.

nv	Print the number of variables in the DRS file.
open <i>DRS-dictionary-file</i>	Open a DRS file ('.dic' extension is optional). Only one file may be open at a time. If a file is currently open, it is closed before the new file is opened.
print [<i>variable</i>][(<i>user-dimension-ranges</i>)]	Print a portion of a variable, using user dimension ranges.
printi [<i>variable</i>][(<i>index-dimension-ranges</i>)]	Print a portion of a variable, using index dimension ranges.
quit	Quit DRSED.
range <i>dimension-number</i> [<i>variable</i>]	Print the first and last values of a dimension of a variable. The <i>dimension-number</i> is an integer from 1 to 4.
set [source name title units] [<i>dimension-number</i>] [<i>variable</i>] = <i>string</i>	Set the source comments, name, title, or units of a variable, or dimension of a variable, to <i>string</i> . If <i>string</i> contains blanks or non-alphanumeric characters, it should be bracketed by double quotes. The <i>dimension-number</i> is an integer from 1 to 4.
shape [<i>variable</i>]	Print the lengths of the dimensions of a variable.
source [<i>dimension-number</i>] [<i>variable</i>]	Print the source comments for a variable (if no dimension-number is specified) or a dimension of a variable. The dimension number, if specified, is an integer from 1 to 4.
time [<i>variable</i>]	Print the timestamp of a variable. The timestamp is the date and time when the variable was written.
title [<i>dimension-number</i>] [<i>variable</i>]	Print the title for a variable (if no dimension-number is specified) or a dimension of a variable. The dimension number, if specified, is an integer from 1 to 4.
type [<i>variable</i>]	Print the data type of a variable.
write [<i>variable</i>][(<i>user-dimension-ranges</i>)]	Write a portion of a variable to the ASCII output file specified by the most recent create command.
units [<i>dimension-number</i>] [<i>variable</i>]	

Print the units of a variable (if no dimension-number is specified) or a dimension of a variable. The dimension number, if specified, is an integer from 1 to 4.

1.4 A sample DRSED session

In this example, the DRS data file `installdemo.dat` and dictionary file `installdemo.dic` exist in the current directory. Note that it is the `.dic` file which is specified on the command line; the extension may be left off. Comments are bracketed by `/* */`.

```
% drsed installdemo
/* Installdemo.dat contains three variables: hflxsen, evapsfc, and prtot. The latitude and longitude
variables are dimension variables. */
>list
hflxsen: Sensible Heat Flux
evapsfc: Evaporation at the Surface
prtot: Total Precipitation
latitude:
longitude:

/* prtot is a 2-dimensional variable, defined on a 64 x 32 lon-lat grid. */
>describe prtot
Name: prtot
Title: Total Precipitation
Source: means jun 01-0*
Units: mm/day
Data type: R*4
Shape: 64 32
Date: 6/17/91 12:49:28
** Dimension 1 **
  Name: longitude
  Title:
  Source:
  Units: degrees
  Spacing: uneven
  Length: 64
  Values:
(   1):      0      5.625      11.25      16.875      22.5      28.125
(   7):     33.75     39.375      45         50.625     56.25     61.875
(  13):     67.5     73.125     78.75     84.375     90         95.625
(  19):    101.25    106.875    112.5     118.125    123.75    129.375
(  25):     135     140.625    146.25    151.875    157.5     163.125
(  31):    168.75    174.375     180       185.625    191.25    196.875
(  37):    202.5     208.125    213.75    219.375     225       230.625
(  43):    236.25    241.875    247.5     253.125    258.75    264.375
(  49):     270     275.625    281.25    286.875    292.5     298.125
(  55):    303.75    309.375     315       320.625    326.25    331.875
(  61):    337.5     343.125    348.75    354.375
** Dimension 2 **
  Name: latitude
  Title:
  Source:
  Units: degrees
```

```

Spacing: uneven
Length: 32
Values:
(   1):  85.76058  80.26878  74.74454  69.21297  63.67863  58.14295
(   7):  52.60653  47.06964  41.53246  35.99508  30.45755  24.91993
(  13):  19.38223  13.84448  8.306703  2.768903 -2.768903 -8.306703
(  19): -13.84448 -19.38223 -24.91993 -30.45755 -35.99508 -41.53246
(  25): -47.06964 -52.60653 -58.14295 -63.67863 -69.21297 -74.74454
(  31): -80.26878 -85.76058

/* print the values of prtot (the current variable) corresponding to longitudes 0 to 78.75 inclusive,
at latitude 85.761 */
>print (0:78.75,85.761)

(   0, 85.76058):  0.8563904  0.7936714  0.7127936  0.631571  0.5231538  0.4113186
( 33.75, 85.76058):  0.3023199  0.2124669  0.1443063  0.09259053  0.07897226  0.07060092
( 67.5, 85.76058):  0.06606676  0.06446455  0.06539725

/* print the values of evapsfc at the 32nd longitude value (174.375), all values of latitude */
>printi evapsfc(32,*)

( 174.375, 85.76058):  0.2714112  0.240286  0.3116955  0.361038  0.08834729  0.7809513
( 174.375, 52.60653):  0.5425962  0.4130771  0.6355915  1.937129  3.33848  4.22867
( 174.375, 19.38223):  3.771547  3.911182  3.270171  3.083863  3.503759  3.983524
( 174.375, -13.84448):  7.598406  5.770195  3.584856  2.989901  3.465111  3.941133
( 174.375, -47.06964):  3.105994  1.991641  0.8699899  0.8132942  0.1711955  0.4325453
( 174.375, -80.26878):  0.07474341  0.2827082

>quit
%
```

Translating data files into DRS format: DRSTRAN

2.1 Concepts

DRSTRAN is a utility program for translating data into DRS format. DRSTRAN can read data from one or more input files in a variety of formats, and combine the data into one or more DRS output files. DRSTRAN may also be used to merge multiple DRS files, or extract portions of data from DRS files.

DRSTRAN may be customized to read specialized formats, by linking in new input routines. An input routine may be written in C, Fortran, or C++.

2.1.1 Data model

All data is associated with *variables*, which are arrays of one to four dimensions. A variable may be real, integer, or string valued. The set of dimensions of a variable is termed its *domain*.

DRSTRAN reads all data from a set of one or more *input files*.

2.1.2 Input Files and Formats

Input files are said to have a certain *format* if they structure and represent data in the same way. DRSTRAN reads data from an input file of a particular format, via the *input-routine* for that format. An input routine is a function, written in C, Fortran, or C++, which reads data for a variable from an input file of a particular format. DRSTRAN handles the mechanics of creating and writing data to the DRS output files.

Table lists the predefined formats provided by DRSTRAN.

TABLE 5

Predefined DRSTRAN Formats

Format	Description	Language
ASCII	Blank separated ASCII floating-point values	C
BIN	Binary unformatted; integer, floating-point, and/or character	C
FBIN	Fortran unformatted; integer or floating-point	Fortran
DRS	DRS format; integer, floating-point, and/or character	C++

These predefined formats are usually sufficient to handle routine conversion tasks. If an input file is not in one of the predefined formats (or cannot easily be converted to such a format), then it is necessary to write a customized input routine and link it to DRSTRAN. A description of writing input routines appears later in this document.

The language associated with a format is specified in the Formats section of the metafile. (See section 2.4.5 on page 19.) The format of each input file is specified in the InputFiles section. (See section 2.4.6 on page 20.)

2.1.3 Extended dimensions

A variable may optionally have a special dimension, called the *extended dimension* of the variable, which spans multiple files. For climatological data this is often the time dimension. Extended dimensions are specified in the Variables section of the metafile. (See section 2.4.9 on page 23.)

For example, let variable V have domain {Longitude, Latitude, Time}. If Time is the extended dimension of V, then for every timepoint T in Time, all values of V associated with T are contained in the same file, but data for V at two distinct timepoints need not be in the same file.

A variable may have at most one extended dimension. Different variables may have the same or different extended dimensions.

If a variable does not have an extended dimension, then all data for that variable must be in a single input file.

The associations between variables, input files, and extended dimension values are described in the FileVariables section of the metafile. (See section 2.4.10 on page 24.)

2.2 Running DRSTRAN

The syntax of the DRSTRAN command line is

```
% drstran [cpp-directives] metafile
```

where

cpp-directives are command-line directives acceptable to the Unix C preprocessor **cpp**. (See “CPP preprocessing” on page 26 for a more complete description).

metafile is the pathname of the ASCII metafile.

For example, to run drstran using the metafile bin.met, replacing all occurrences of the token ‘IN’ with ‘input.txt’, and all occurrences of the token ‘OUT’ with ‘test’, type

```
% drstran -DIN=input.txt -DOUT=test bin.met
```

2.2.1 System specifics

On cirrus, the DRSTRAN executable and predefined metafiles are located in the /usr/local/drs/util directory. This directory should be added to your \$path variable, in .cshrc or .login.

To be able to run DRSTRAN on the PCMDI network, the workstation must have the **cirrus** directory /usr/CC mounted, and the directory /usr/CC/sun4 specified **first** in the environment variable LD_LIBRARY_PATH; e.g., in .cshrc or .login:

```
setenv LD_LIBRARY_PATH /usr/CC/sun4:etc...
```

The directory name corresponding to /usr/CC may differ on different workstations; consult the system manager for details.

2.3 Metafiles

A metafile is an ASCII file which specifies:

- information about the data being translated,
- input files and their format(s),
- ordering of variables within files, and
- which file(s) contain the specified variables.

The information in the metafile controls the execution of DRSTRAN and provides the additional descriptive information required to build a DRS file.

2.3.1 Order of execution

The metafile controls the order in which data is read from input files and written to output files. This order is implicitly declared by the order in which the following objects are specified:

- Variables (in the Variables section)
- Extended dimensions (in the Variables section)
- Extended dimension values (in the Dimensions section)

DRSTRAN reads data from input files based on these orderings. In the common situation where no variables span files, i.e., no extended dimensions are used, the DRSTRAN algorithm is:

1. Write the dimensions;
2. For each variable V, in the order specified in the Variables section of the metafile:
 - a. Let F be the input file containing V (specified in the FileVariables section of the metafile);
 - b. Read V from F;
 - c. Write V to the output file specified for V (in the Variables section of the metafile)

If more than one output file appears in the Variables section, this algorithm is repeated for each output file.

See section 2.7.3 on page 34 for a description of the DRSTRAN algorithm in the more general case where extended dimensions are used.

2.3.2 Data ordering

2.3.2.1 Ordering of variables

Typically, the order in which variables are defined in the Variables section (section 2.4.9 on page 23) is significant. **If the input routine associated with an input file format uses sequential I/O, then the variables must appear in the Variables section of the metafile in the order in which they occur in the input file.** Otherwise, the DRS output file will be incorrect. The predefined formats which use sequential I/O are the ASCII, unformatted binary (BIN), and Fortran unformatted binary (FBIN) formats.

The ordering is irrelevant for DRS input files (DRSINPUT), as DRS uses random-access I/O.

2.3.2.2 Ordering of variable data

The ordering of dimensions within the Domain specifier is also significant. **The first dimension specified is the dimension whose values vary most rapidly in the input file, the second dimension varies next most rapidly, and the last dimension varies least rapidly.** This corresponds to Fortran ordering of arrays. For DRS files, the ordering

should match the order of the dimensions in the DRS file. This can be determined using the **drsed** utility.

2.4 Metafile Syntax

2.4.1 Definitions

An *identifier* is a character string which begins with a letter or underscore, and contains no blanks. Following the first letter, a character may be a letter, number, underscore, dash (-), pound sign (#), or period.

A *number* is an integer or floating-point number. Exponents are represented with standard 'E' notation. Examples of legal numbers are: 10, 10.0, -10.0, and 1.0e1.

A *pathname* is any legal UNIX pathname of a file. For example, '/data/jones/test.dat', and 'sample1.txt', are legal pathnames. A pathname may begin with a period.

A *string* is a sequence of characters, optionally bracketed by double quotes. If the *string* contains blanks, it must appear within quotes. To include a quote within a string, escape it with a backslash (\).

2.4.2 Metafile Structure

A DRSTRAN metafile is an editable, ASCII file. By convention, metafles have a file extension '.met', although any extension may be used. DRSTRAN treats the metafle as a stream of white-space delimited tokens. (White space is defined as any number of consecutive blanks, tabs, newlines, or formfeeds). Before parsing the metafle, DRSTRAN passes it through **cpp**, the Unix C preprocessor. Consequently all the **cpp** directives, such as **#include** and **#define**, may be used in a metafle. This is especially useful for specifying command line arguments, and for including predefined formats, dimensions, and domains (see section 2.5 on page 26).

A DRSTRAN metafle consists of seven sections: Formats, Inputfiles, Dimensions, Domains, Variables, FileVariables, and (optionally) Escape. The ordering of the sections is:

Formats-Section

Inputfiles-Section

Dimensions-Section

Domains-Section

Variables-Section

FileVariables-Section

[Escape-Section]

There may be more than one of any given section, provided that the proper ordering of sections is maintained. This allows predefined sections to be included from external files via the **#include** directive.

Each section (with the exception of the Escape section) is made up of a sequence of *specifiers*, enclosed in braces ({ }) and separated by white space. A *specifier* is a sequence of *fields*, separated by commas. Fields may be mandatory (position-dependent) or optional (position-independent). All fields have a keyword associated with them. *Mandatory fields* appear at the start of a specifier, and must appear in the order specified, even if the keyword is used. *Optional fields* in a specifier always follow the mandatory fields, and must have a keyword. The generic syntax of a *specifier* is:

$$\text{specifier} == \{ \text{mandatory-field}_1, \dots, \text{mandatory-field}_m, \text{optional-field}_1, \dots, \text{optional-field}_n \}$$

$$\text{mandatory-field} == [\text{keyword} =] \text{field-value}$$

$$\text{optional-field} == [\text{keyword} =] \text{field-value}$$

2.4.3 Keywords

DRSTRAN recognizes certain keywords within a metafile. Keywords are non-case-sensitive. It is recommended that their use as identifiers be avoided. They may be used within quoted strings and comments without problem. Table 6 lists the reserved identifiers.

TABLE 6

DRSTRAN Keywords

Clanguage	Cplusplus	Dimensions	Domain	Domains
Escape	Evenvalues	File	Filevariables	Float
Format	Formats	Fortran	Id	Inputfiles
Int	Language	Name	Oname	Source
String	Title	Type	Units	Values
Variable	Variables	Xdim		

2.4.4 Comments

Any characters appearing within /* and */ are treated as comments. Such comments may span multiple lines, that is, newlines may appear within the comment. Comments may appear anywhere within a metafile, including within sections.

Characters following ‘//’ are treated as single-line comments, which are terminated by a newline.

2.4.5 Formats section

The Formats section specifies the language in which the input routine is written. Pre-defined formats are described in the file **formats.met**, which can be included in the metafile. The syntax of the Formats section is

Format-Section ==
Formats = { *Format-specifier*₁ ... *Format-specifier*_n }

where

Format-specifier == { *Format-name*, *Language* }
Format-name == *identifier*
Language == [*Language* =] CLANGUAGE | FORTRAN | CPLUSPLUS

For example,

Formats = { { ASCII, CLANGUAGE } { FBIN, FORTRAN } }

2.4.6 InputFiles section

The InputFiles section defines the input files and their formats. DRSTRAN reads data from an input file via the input routine associated with the file's format. The syntax of the Inputfiles sections is

Inputfiles-section ==
Inputfiles = { *Input-file-specifier*₁ ... *Input-file-specifier*_n }

where

Input-file-specifier ==
{ [*File* =] *pathname*, [*Format* =] *Format-name* }

The *Format-name* must appear in a preceding Formats section.

For example,

Inputfiles = { { /data/test/asciidemo1.txt, ASCII }
{ /data/test/asciidemo2.txt, ASCII } }

2.4.7 Dimensions section

The Dimensions section describes all dimensions of variables to be translated via DRSTRAN. This descriptive information includes representation (even spacing or uneven spacing), name, units, and dimension values. The dimension vector is a real-valued, strictly monotonic vector.

The syntax of this section is:

Dimensions-Section ==
Dimensions = { *dimension-specifier*₁ ... *dimension-specifier*_n }

where

dimension-specifier ==
{ *dimension-id*, *values-field* | *even-values-field* [, *name-field*] [, *units-field*] }

```

dimension-id ==
[Id = ] dimension-identifier

values-field ==
Values = { value-or-dimension1[,] ... [,] value-or-dimensionn }

even-values-field ==
EvenValues = { first-value, length, npoints }

value-or-dimension == number | dimension-identifier

name-field == [Name =] string

units-field == [Units =] string

```

If the dimension vector is represented by a value list (Values = ...), then the values must be strictly monotonic. A previously defined dimension-identifier may be used, in which case the values of that dimension are ‘spliced’ into the vector at that point. In either case, an error is issued if the values are not strictly monotonic, increasing or decreasing.

If a dimension is represented as evenly-spaced (Values = ...) then the vector is represented by the triplet { *first-value*, *length*, *npoints* }, where

```

first-value is the initial value of the dimension,
length = interval * npoints, and
npoints = number of points in the dimension.

```

If the dimension values are decreasing, specify a negative *length*.

If the *name-field* is omitted, it defaults to the *dimension-identifier*. The default units are “none”.

2.4.7.1 Examples

1. The T42 longitude has 128 points, starting at 0.0, ending at 357.1875, with an interval of 2.8125 degrees. The evenly-spaced representation may be used, with *first-value* = 0.0, *length* = 2.8125*128=360.0, and *npoints* = 128. The *dimension-specifier* would be:

```

{T42_LONG, EvenValues = {0.0,360.0,128},Name=Longitude,
Units=Degrees}

```

2. A latitude dimension goes from 90N to 90S, at 4 degree intervals, for a total of 46 points. In this case, *length* = -4*46 = -184 (the negative sign indicates a decreasing vector), and the *dimension-specifier* is

```

{LAT,EvenValues = {90,-184,46}, Name=Latitude,Units=Degrees}

```

3. A dimension has values {10,8,4,1}. A related dimension has values {10,8,4,1,0}. These can be specified as:

```

Dimensions = {
{SAMPLE1, Values = {10,8,4,1}}
{SAMPLE2, Values = {SAMPLE1,0}}
}

```

-
4. A variable is defined for hour=100,101, 102, and 103. The data for hour 100 and 101 are in two separate files, and the data for hours 102 and 103 are combined in another file. Consequently, ‘Time’ will be the extended dimension for this variable, and it is necessary to define identifiers for the sub-dimensions for later reference in the Variables and FileVariables sections. The ‘Time’ dimension must be defined in terms of these subdimensions:

```
Dimensions = {  
  {T100,Values={ 100}}  
  {T101,Values={ 101}}  
  {T102X3,Values={ 102,103}}  
  {Time,Values={T100,T101,T102X3},Units=Hours}}
```

2.4.8 Domains section

A *domain* is a set of one to four dimensions. The Domains section specifies the domains associated with the input variables.

The syntax of the Domains section is

```
Domain-section ==  
Domains = {domain-specifier1 ... domain-specifiern}
```

where

```
domain-specifier == {[Id =] domain-identifier, [Dimensions = ] dimensions-  
list}
```

```
dimensions-list == {domain-identifier1| dimension-identifier1, ..., domain-iden-  
tifiern| dimension-identifiern}
```

If a domain-identifier appears in the dimensions-list, it must have already been defined in a previous specifier, in which case it’s dimension-list is ‘spliced’ into the current domain. Similarly, all dimension-identifiers must be appear in a preceding Dimensions section.

For example:

```
Domains = {  
  {T42_2D,{T42_LONG,T42_LAT}}  
  {T42_3D,{T42_2D,TIME}}}
```

The ordering of dimensions within the Domain specifier is significant. **The first dimension specified must be the dimension whose values vary most rapidly in the data returned from the input routine, the second dimension varies next most rapidly, and the last dimension varies least rapidly.** This corresponds to Fortran ordering of arrays. Since the input routines for ASCII, BIN, and FBIN files return data in the order found in the input files, the dimension orders must match the data ordering in the input files. For DRSINPUT files, the ordering should match the order of the dimensions of the variable in the DRS file. This can be determined using the **drsed** utility. If a dimension is to be used as an extended dimension, it must be the last dimension specified in the domain for that variable.

In the previous example, the data in the input file for a variable with domain T42_3D should have longitude varying most rapidly, latitude next-most rapidly, and time least rapidly. That is, the first data values in the input file should correspond to all longitude values for the first latitude and first time, followed by all longitude values for the second latitude and first time, and so on.

2.4.9 Variables section

The Variables section defines all the variables to be translated into the DRS output file(s), and implicitly defines the order in which the variables will be read from the input files.

The syntax of the Variables section is

```
Variables-Section ==  
Variables = {Variable-specifier1 ... Variable-specifiern}
```

where

```
Variable-specifier ==  
{[Id = ] variable-name, [Domain = ] domain-identifier, [Units = ] variable-  
units, [Type = ] variable-type, [File = ] output-filename [, Oname = output-vari-  
able-name] [, Title = variable-title] [, Xdim = extended-dimension-ID] [,  
Source = variable-source]}
```

variable-name is the name of the variable which is passed to the input routine, and which is referenced in the FileVariables section. By default, it is also the name of the variable written to the output DRS file, unless overridden by the optional *output-variable-name* field.

domain-identifier is an *identifier* for the domain of the variable, as specified in a preceding Domains section.

variable-units is a *string* of up to 40 characters, describing the variable units.

variable-type == Float | Int | {String, *byte-length*}
indicating the datatype of the variable. *byte-length* is the number of bytes in each element of a string-valued variable.

output-filename is the pathname of the DRS output file for the variable, omitting the .dic or .dat filetype.

output-variable-name is a *string* of up to 16 characters, indicating the name of the variable to be written to the DRS output file. If omitted, the *variable-name* is used. This field is useful if the name of the variable in the input file differs from that of the output file, or if the output name contains blanks.

variable-title is a *string* of up to 80 characters, indicating the long-name of the variable. The default is a blank string.

variable-source is a comment *string* of up to 120 characters. The default is a blank string.

extended-dimension-ID is an *identifier* of a dimension, appearing in a preceding Dimensions section, indicating which dimension (if any) of the variable extends across multiple files. Absence of this field indicates that all values of the variable are contained in the single input file specified for the variable in the FileVariables section. If defined, the *extended-dimension-ID* must be one of the identifiers used to define the domain of the variable.

The order of the Variable-specifiers is important: the order of the specifiers is the order in which the variables are read from the input routine(s), and written to the DRS output file. Consequently, if the input routine uses sequential I/O (e.g., ASCII, BIN, or FBIN) then this order must match the input file data. It is the user's responsibility to verify that proper ordering is specified.

As with all optional specifiers, the optional fields (Oname, Title, Xdim, and Source) may appear in any order after the mandatory fields.

2.4.9.1 Examples

For example, the floating point variable 'prtot' is total precipitation generated during a resolution study run. The variable is defined on a T42 domain identified in the Domains section as T42_2D. The variable will be written to a DRS file 'test.dat', using the name prtot. The *Variable-specifier* would be:

```
{prtot,T42_2D,units="mm/day",type=float,file=test,title="Total precipitation",source="Resolution study."}
```

Note that the units are enclosed in quotes, since they contain a nonalphanumeric character.

As another example, suppose that in the previous example, the variable prtot is defined on a three-dimensional domain T42_3D, and the Time dimension of T42_3D spans multiple files; the variable is to be written to file junk2.dat, using the name 'precip'. The *Variable-specifier* would be:

```
{prtot,T42_3D,units="mm/day",type=float,file=junk,oname=precip,title="Total precipitation",source="Resolution study.",xdim=Time}
```

2.4.10 FileVariables section

The FileVariables section of the metafile specifies which input files contain each variable defined in the Variables section. In addition, if a variable has an extended dimension, the FileVariables section specifies which input file contains the variable for each value of the extended dimension.

The syntax of the FileVariables section is:

```
FileVariables-section ==  
FileVariables = {File-variable-specifier1 ... File-variable-specifiern}
```

where

```
File-variable-specifier ==  
{[Variable =] variable-identifier | variable-identifier-list, [File = ] input-filename, [Xdim = subdimension-identifier]}
```

```
variable-identifier-list ==  
{variable-identifier1,...,variable-identifiern}
```

A *variable-identifier* is the identifier of a variable appearing in the Variables section. Each variable in the Variables section must appear in at least one *File-variable-specifier*.

A *subdimension-identifier* is an identifier of a dimension, defined in a previous Dimensions section, which is a sub-dimension of the variable's extended dimension, that is, the *subdimension-identifier* appears in the *values-field* of the extended dimension. If the variable does not have an extended dimension, then this field is not required.

2.4.10.1 Examples

For example, suppose that variables prtot and evapsfc are in file input1.txt, and variable hflxsen is in file input2.txt. The *FileVariables-section* would be:

```
FileVariables = {  
  {prtot,evapsfc},input1.txt}  
  {hflxsen,input2.txt}  
}
```

As another example, suppose that in the previous example, variable prtot has an extended dimension of Time, defined in the Dimensions section as

```
{Time,Values={T100,T101,T102X3},Units=Hours}
```

The values of prtot corresponding to the subdimensions T100,T101, and T102X3 are in files input100.txt, input101.txt, and input102X3.txt, respectively. As before, variable evapsfc is in file input1.txt, and hflxsen is in input2.txt. Then the *FileVariables-section* would be:

```
FileVariables = {  
  {prtot,input100.txt,T100}  
  {prtot,input101.txt,T101}  
  {prtot,input102X3,T102X3}  
  {evapsfc,input1.txt}  
  {hflxsen,input2.txt}  
}
```

2.4.11 Escape Section

The optional escape section provides a means for communicating with the input routine. This section consists of a list of integers, floating point numbers, and strings appearing in any order. DRSTRAN places the values in three separate internal lists: integers, floating-point values, and strings or identifiers, which can be accessed by the input routine. Whether an Escape section is required depends on the requirements of for a given format. If the Escape section is used, the list of escape values must be nonempty.

More formally, the syntax of the Escape section is:

```
Escape-section ==  
Escape = { escape-value1, ..., escape-valuen }  
escape-value == number | string | identifier
```

One use of the Escape section is to pass a missing-data flag to the input routine. For example, when DRSTRAN reads data from a BIN (binary unformatted) file, it checks the Escape values for an integer followed by a missing-data flag. If found, it translates all floating-point numbers with that value to the DRS missing-data flag (1.0e20). A specification of

```
Escape = { 1, -99.9 }
```

will cause all floating-point values of -99.9 found in the BIN format input file to be treated as missing-data values.

2.5 CPP preprocessing

Before parsing a metafile, DRSTRAN passes it through the UNIX C preprocessor **cpp**. Complete documentation for **cpp** is available in the UNIX documentation set. This section only describes a few of the most commonly used features of **cpp**. All **cpp** directives start with a point sign (#) in column one.

```
#define name token-string
```

Replace subsequent instances of *name* with *token-string*.

```
#include "filename"
```

Read in the contents of *filename* at this location.

Two of the frequently used command-line options are the **-D** and **-I** options:

```
-Dname=def
```

Define *name* as if by a **#define** directive. This is the same as

```
#define name def
```

```
-Idir
```

Insert *dir* into the search path for **#include** files.

2.5.1 Formats.met

The file `formats.met` contains specifications for the predefined formats ASCII, BIN, DRS, and FBIN. This file may be included with the **cpp** directive

```
#include "/usr/local/drs/util/formats.met"
```

Alternatively, the file may be included with the directive

```
#include "formats.met"
```

and the directory specified with a -I command line option.

2.5.2 Domains.met

The file domains.met contains dimension and domain specifications for a variety of commonly used grids. This file may be included with the **cpp** directive

```
#include "/usr/local/drs/util/domains.met"
```

Alternatively, the file may be included with the directive

```
#include "domains.met"
```

and the directory specified with a -I command line option.

Table 7 lists the predefined dimension identifiers in the domains.met file.

TABLE 7

Predefined DRSTRAN dimension identifiers

Identifier	Description
T21_LON	64 points, 0.0 to 360.0
T21_GAUSS_LAT	32 points, N to S
T42_LON	128 points, 0.0 to 360.0
T42_GAUSS_LAT	64 points, N to S
T63_LON	192 points, 0.0 to 360.0
T63_GAUSS_LAT	96 points, N to S
T106_LON	320 points, 0.0 to 360.0
T106_GAUSS_LAT	160 points, N to S
JAN, FEB, ..., DEC	1, 2, ..., 12, respectively

Table 8 lists the predefined domain identifiers in the domains.met file.

TABLE 8

Predefined DRSTRAN domain identifiers

Identifier	Description
T21_ECMWF	{T21_LON, T21_GAUSS_LAT}
T42_ECMWF	{T42_LON, T42_GAUSS_LAT}
T63_ECMWF	{T63_LON, T63_GAUSS_LAT}
T106_ECMWF	{T106_LON, T106_GAUSS_LAT}

2.6 Predefined Formats

2.6.1 ASCII

An ASCII format file consists of a blank-separated set of ASCII values in floating-point format. Integer values will be converted to floating-point. Data may be read from an input file or piped into DRSTRAN. This format is defined in **formats.met**.

If an Escape section of the form

Escape={*missing-data-value* [,*delta*]}

is present, then all numbers equal to the *missing-data-value* +/- *delta* will be translated to the DRS missing-data value 1.0e20. The *missing-data-value* and *delta* value must contain a decimal point and/or an exponent, otherwise they will not be recognized as floating-point. If the *missing-data-value* is not present, no translations will occur. The default *delta* is 0.001.

Variable specifiers in the metafile must be in the same order as the data appears in the input file.

See section B.2 on page 49 for a sample metafile to be used with an ASCII input file.

2.6.2 BIN

A BIN format file is an unformatted binary file consisting of raw data values (i.e., no control words; if the file was written via Fortran unformatted sequential I/O, use FBIN instead). Data may be integer, floating-point, or character. This format is defined in **formats.met**.

If an Escape section of the form

Escape={*integer*, *missing-data-value* [,*delta*]}

is present, where *integer* is any integer value, then all numbers equal to the *missing-data-value* +/- *delta* will be translated to the DRS missing-data value 1.0e20. The *missing-data-value* and *delta* must contain a decimal point and/or an exponent, otherwise they will not be recognized as floating-point. If the *missing-data-value* is not present, no translations will occur. The default *delta* is 0.001.

Variable specifiers in the metafile must be in the same order as the data appears in the input file.

See section B.1 on page 48 for a sample metafile to be used with a BIN input file.

2.6.3 DRSSINPUT

The identifier DRSSINPUT indicates an input file in DRS format. DRSTRAN may be used to concatenate or extract data from DRS input files.

Note that DRSTRAN uses the dimension and domain information in the metafile, rather than in the DRS file. This allows extraction specifying portions of dimensions.

Source, title, and units information may be copied from the DRS input file by using a “%%” field in the variable specifier. For example

```
{prtot,T42_3D,units="%%",float,test,title="%%",source="%%"}
```

copies the units, title, and source for variable ‘prtot’ from the DRS input file.

If an Escape section of the form

```
Escape={missing-data-value [,delta]}
```

is present, then all numbers equal to the *missing-data-value* +/- *delta* will be translated to the DRS missing-data value 1.0e20. The *missing-data-value* and *delta* value must contain a decimal point and/or an exponent, otherwise they will not be recognized as floating-point. If the *missing-data-value* is not present, no translations will occur. The default *delta* is 0.001.

Since DRS uses random-access I/O, variable specifiers may appear in any order.

2.6.4 FBIN

An FBIN file is an unformatted binary file written via Fortran unformatted sequential I/O. (Fortran writes control words to such files.) Data may be four-byte integer or floating-point. Unless specified in the Escape section, it is assumed that each variable is in one and only one record. Character data is not supported in this format.

If an Escape section of the form

```
Escape={1, missing-data-value [,delta] [,multi-record-specifier]}
```

is present, then all numbers equal to the *missing-data-value* +/- *delta* will be translated to the DRS missing-data value 1.0e20. The *missing-data-value* and *delta* must contain a decimal point and/or an exponent, otherwise they will not be recognized as floating-point. If the *missing-data-value* is not present, no translations will occur. The default *delta* is 0.001.

If a *multi-record-specifier* is present with the form

```
multi-record-specifier ==  
1,nrec,nskip,nread
```

where *nrec* is the number of records per variable, *nskip* is the number of four-byte words to skip at the head of each record, and *nread* is the number of four-byte words to read from each record, then it is assumed that each variable is contained in *nrec* contiguous records. A record cannot contain more than one variable.

For example, if each variable is contained in 84 records, and the first 5 words of each record are header words, followed by 10,512 data words, and there is no missing data, then specify

Escape = {0,1,84,5,10512}

The initial 0 indicates that there are no missing data flags in the escape list. If in addition missing data existed, flagged as -99.9, this could be specified by

Escape = {1,-99.9,0.01,1,84,5,10512}

Variable specifiers in the metafile must be in the same order as the data records appear in the input file.

2.7 Adding formats to DRSTRAN

This section describes the process of adding a customized input routine to DRSTRAN. It is assumed that the reader has some experience in programming in C, Fortran, or C++ on a Unix system. This chapter describes the process of adding new routines in C or Fortran, or modifying existing input routines. Adding C++ routines is beyond the scope of this document.

2.7.1 Structure of DRSTRAN

Figure 1 illustrates the structure of the DRSTRAN program.

FIGURE 1

DRSTRAN structure

DRSTRAN consists of the following modules:

- **DRSTRAN** passes the metafile through **cpp**, parses the output from **cpp**, generates the Internal Data Structures, creates the DRS Output Files, uses the information in the metafile to read the data via the Input Routines, one variable at a time, from the Input Files, and copy the data to the Output Files. DRSTRAN is itself written in C++.
- The **Input Routines** comprise the interface between DRSTRAN and the input data. An input routine accepts a variable handle and an input file handle from DRSTRAN, reads the variable from the specified input file, and returns the data to DRSTRAN. The input routine is responsible for opening and closing files as necessary. An input routine may be written in C, Fortran, or C++. The input routine accesses information from the internal data structures via the interface routines.
- The **Interface Routines** are a set of library routines, callable from C, Fortran, or C++, which allow the input routines to access details of the variable structure and input file structure passed as input arguments. Escape arguments are also accessed through these routines.
- There are five **Internal Data Structures** accessible to the input routines: a *variable structure*, which describes the data to be read, an *input file structure* which describes the input file from which to read the data, and three lists of *escape values*, one each for integer, real, and string values.
- The DRS library modules are used to create, write, and close the output DRS file(s).

Table 9 describes the data flows between these modules. Flow numbers refer to Figure 1.

TABLE 9

DRSTRAN data flows

Flow	Description
1	The metafile is passed through cpp , then the result is parsed. The structure of a metafile is described in section 2.4 on page 18.
2	The input routine returns data to DRSTRAN following a successful read, or a flag indicating error.
3	DRSTRAN passes two parameters to the input routine: a variable handle to a structure which describes the data to be read, and an input file handle which describes the input file to read from.
4	Via the interface routines, an input routine can set certain file characteristics, such as file pointers (in C), logical unit numbers (in Fortran), and variable characteristics, such as type, source, output name, title, and units.
5	The input routine can use the interface routines to get various attributes of the file, such as format, pathname, etc. and variable attributes, such as type, number of elements, etc. Escape parameters can also be read.
6	DRSTRAN uses the information in the metafile to create several internal data structures accessible to input routines. Their structure is described in detail below.
7	DRSTRAN uses the DRS library to create the output files and write each variable, as it is read, to the file.

2.7.2 Data structures

Five internal data structures are available to an input routine:

- a Variable structure, which describes the variable to be read,
- a File structure, which describes the input file, and
- three lists of integer, real and string escape values, from the Escape section of the metafile.

2.7.2.1 Variable structure

The variable structure describes the data to be read by the input routine at any given time. Note that, if an extended dimension is used for a variable, this structure will specify the subranges of the extended dimension to be read. A *range* of a dimension is a pair of indices which indicate the first and last indices of the dimension vector corresponding to the data to be read.

TABLE 10

DRSTRAN Variable structure attributes and interface functions

<i>Attribute</i>	<i>Get Set</i>	<i>Interface Function</i>	<i>Description</i>
------------------	----------------	---------------------------	--------------------

DimensionLength	X		GetSlabDimensionLength	Number of elements in a dimension.
DimensionType	X		GetSlabDimensionType	Even or uneven (vector) representation?
DimensionValue	X		GetSlabDimensionValue	Value of a dimension element.
InputName	X		GetSlabInputName	Name to use on input.
Name	X	X	Get/SetSlabInputName	Output file name.
Ndim	X		GetSlabNumberOfDimensions	Number of dimensions of the var.
Nelements	X		GetSlabNelements	Total number of elements to be read.
RangeFirstIndex	X		GetSlabRangeFirstIndex	First index of a dimension subrange.
RangeLastIndex	X		GetSlabRangeLastIndex	Last index of a dimension subrange.
Source	X	X	Get/SetSlabSource	Comments.
Title	X	X	Get/SetSlabTitle	Long variable name.
Type	X	X	Get/SetSlabType	Variable type
Units	X	X	Get/SetSlabUnits	Variable units.

2.7.2.2 File data structure

The file data structure describes the input file from which to read the variable. Note that the input routine is responsible for opening and closing input files. The file pointer and logical unit attributes may be used to store information between invocations of the input routine.

TABLE 11

DRSTRAN File data structure attributes and interface functions

<i>Attribute</i>	<i>Get</i>	<i>Set</i>	<i>Interface Function</i>	<i>Description</i>
Format	X		GetFileFormat	Format identifier
Fp	X	X	Get/SetFileFp	(C only) File pointer
Lun	X	X	Get/SetFileLun	(Fortran only) Logical unit number
Path	X		GetFilePath	File pathname

2.7.2.3 Escape lists

TABLE 12

DRSTRAN Escape list attributes and interface functions

<i>Attribute</i>	<i>Get</i>	<i>Set</i>	<i>Interface Function</i>	<i>Description</i>
NthChar	X		GetNthEscapeChar	Nth entry in string list (1-origin)
NthInt	X		GetNthEscapeInt	Nth entry in integer list (1-origin)
NthReal	X		GetNthEscapeReal	Nth entry in real list (1-origin)

2.7.3 Procedural description

Once the metafile has been parsed, the DRSTRAN algorithm is:

1. Write the dimensions;
2. Read and write the variables having no extended dimension, in the order they appear in the Variables section;
3. For each extended dimension E (in the order they appear in an Xdim field in the Variables section):

For each variable V with extended dimension E (in the order they appear in the Variables section of the metafile):

For each value X in E, starting with the first value defined for E in the Dimensions section:

- Let F be the input file containing data for V at E=X (as specified in the FileVariables section of the metafile);
- Read V, for E=X, from file F;
- Write V, for E=X, to the output file for V (specified in the Variables section of the metafile).

2.7.4 Interface routines

The interface routines provide access to the internal data structures.

2.7.4.1 Fortran interface routines

The arguments *variable* and *file* are the handles which are passed to the input routine. They should only be used as arguments to interface routines.

TABLE 13

DRSTRAN Fortran interface routines

<i>Function</i>	<i>Returns</i>	<i>Description</i>
GetFileFormat(file,character*(*) format)	0	Returns format identifier in format.
GetFileLun(file)	integer	Function returns the logical unit number of the file, or 0 if the file has not yet been opened (by the input routine).
GetFilePath(file, character*1024 path)	0	Returns input file pathname in path.
GetNthEscapeChar(integer n, character*(*) escapeChar)	0	Returns the nth escape string (1-origin).
GetNthEscapeInt(integer n, integer escapeInt)	0	Returns the nth escape integer (1-origin).

GetNthEscapeReal(integer n, real escapeReal)
0 Returns the nth escape real (1-origin).

GetSlabDimensionLength(variable,int dimensionNumber)
integer Function returns length of dimension with 1-origin index dimensionNumber (1 to 4).

GetSlabDimensionType(variable,int dimensionNumber)
integer Function returns 1 if dimension has an equally-spaced representation; 2 for unequally-spaced (vector) representation.

GetSlabDimensionValue(variable,integer dimensionNumber,integer index, real dimensionValue)
0 Returns dimension value with (1-origin) index.

GetSlabInputName(variable, character*16 name)
0 Returns name of variable on input (useful for DRS input files).

GetSlabName(variable,character*16 name)
0 Returns output name of variable.

GetSlabNelements(variable)
integer Function returns number of data elements to read.

GetSlabNumberOfDimensions(variable)
integer Function Returns number of dimensions of the variable.

GetSlabRangeFirstIndex(variable,integer dimensionNumber)
integer Function Returns index of the first value of the dimension range.

GetSlabRangeLastIndex(variable,integer dimensionNumber)
integer Function returns index of the last value of the dimension range.

GetSlabSource(variable, character*120 source)
0 Returns variable comments.

GetSlabTitle(variable, chracter*80 title)
0 Returns variable long name in title.

GetSlabType(variable, integer type, integer byteLength)
0 Returns integer representing type (possible values are IDR-
S_USER, IDRS_IEEE_R4, IDRS_CRAY_R8,
IDRS_I4, IDRS_I8, and IDRS_ASCII, as defined in
drscdf.h), and the number of bytes in each data element.

GetSlabUnits(variable, character*40 units)
0 Returns variable units.

SetFileLun(file,integer lun)
0 Set logical unit number to lun.

SetSlabName(variable,character*16 name)
0 Set variable output name to name.

SetSlabSource(variable, character*120 source)

	0	Set variable comments to source.
SetSlabTitle(variable,character*80 title)		
	0	Set variable title.
SetSlabType(variable, integer type, integer byteLength)		
	0	Set variable type to IDRS_USER, IDRS_IEEE_R4, IDRS_CRAY_R8, IDRS_I4, IDRS_I8, or IDRS_ASCII, as defined in drsdef.h; element byteLength is ignored unless the variable type is IDRS_USER or IDRS_ASCII.
SetSlabUnits(variable, character*40 units)		
	0	Set variable units.

2.7.4.2 C interface routines

Table 14, “DRSTRAN C interface routines,” lists the interface routines which may be accessed within a C input routine. The arguments *variable* and *file* are the handles which are passed to the input routine. They should only be used as arguments to interface routines.

TABLE 14

DRSTRAN C interface routines

<i>Function</i>	<i>Returns</i>	<i>Description</i>
GetFileFormat(file)	char *	Format identifier.
GetFileFp(file)	FILE *	Input file pointer.
GetFilePath(file)	char *	Input file pathname.
GetNthEscapeChar(int n)	char *	Nth value in escape strings list (1-origin).
GetNthEscapeInt(int n)	int *	Nth value in escape integers list (1-origin).
GetNthEscapeReal(int n)	real *	Nth value in escape reals list (1-origin).
GetSlabDimensionLength(variable,int dimensionNumber)	int	Length of dimension dimensionNumber (1-origin).
GetSlabDimensionType(variable,int dimensionNumber)	int	Returns 1 if dimension has an equally-spaced representation; 2 for unequally-spaced (vector) representation.
GetSlabDimensionValue(variable,int dimensionNumber,int index,float *dimensionValue)	0	Return pointer to the dimension value with (1-origin) index.
GetSlabInputName(variable)	char *	Name of variable on input (useful for DRS input files).
GetSlabName(variable)	char *	Output name of variable.
GetSlabNelements(variable)	int	Returns number of data elements to read.
GetSlabNumberOfDimensions(variable)		

	int	Returns number of dimensions of the variable.
GetSlabRangeFirstIndex(variable,int dimensionNumber)	int	Returns index of the first value of the dimension range.
GetSlabRangeLastIndex(variable,int dimensionNumber)	int	Returns index of the last value of the dimension range.
GetSlabSource(variable) char *		Returns variable comments.
GetSlabTitle(variable) char *		Returns variable long name (title).
GetSlabType(variable, int *type, int *byteLength)	0	Returns pointer to integer representing type (possible values are IDRS_USER, IDRS_IEEE_R4, IDRS_CRAY_R8, IDRS_I4, IDRS_I8, and IDRS_ASCII, as defined in drscdf.h), and a pointer to the number of bytes in each data element.
GetSlabUnits(variable) char *		Returns variable units.
SetFileFp(file,FILE *fp) 0		Set file pointer to fp.
SetSlabName(variable,char *name)	0	Set variable output name to name.
SetSlabSource(variable, char *source)	0	Set variable comments to source.
SetSlabTitle(variable,char *title)	0	Set variable title.
SetSlabType(variable, int type, int byteLength)	0	Set variable type to IDRS_USER, IDRS_IEEE_R4, IDRS_CRAY_R8, IDRS_I4, IDRS_I8, or IDRS_ASCII, as defined in drscdf.h; element byte-length is ignored unless the variable type is IDRS_USER or IDRS_ASCII.
SetSlabUnits(variable, char *units)	0	Set variable units.

2.7.5 Input routines

An input routine accepts as input a variable handle and an input file handle, returns the data, and a function value of 0 for success or 1 for read failure. Declarations for the interface routines are in the include files dtinterc.h for C routines, and dtinterf.h for Fortran routines.

A C input routine has the form:

```
#include "dtinterc.h"
int routine-name(variable, file, data)
void *variable, *file;
```

```
float *data;
{...}
```

A Fortran input routine has the form:

```
integer function routine-name(variable, file, databuf)
integer variable, file
real databuf(*)

#include "dtinterf.h"
...
end
```

2.7.5.1 Input routine template

At a minimum, an input routine must read the variable data from the input file, returning the data in the 'data' array. A somewhat more complete template for an input file would be:

#include interface function declarations

Check the file format identifier.

Open the input file, if necessary.

Get the number of data elements to read.

Read the data into the output data argument. Return 1 if an error occurred.

Check the escape values for presence of a missing-data flag. If present, replace all data values equal to the missing-data flag.

Return a function value of 0 (success).

2.7.6 Linking to DRSTRAN

2.7.6.1 System Specifics

C and Fortran source code, and libraries for DRSTRAN are located in directory

```
/usr/local/drs/util/drstransrc
```

on the PCMDI **cirrus** machine.

Figure 4 shows a sample Makefile for drstran. To make a new version of DRSTRAN, copy the sources to your own directory, make the appropriate changes to the Makefile, and type:

```
make drstran
```

When DRS is installed from the installation tape, DRSTRAN sources are located by default in directory

```
$DIR/drs/src/drstran
```

where \$DIR is the top-level installation directory.

2.7.6.2 Adding a new input routine

To add a new input routine to DRSTRAN:

1. Create the input routine in the format described in the section “Input routines” on page 37,
2. Modify the routine **dtreadc.c** (C language) or **dtreadf.F** (Fortran language), as indicated in Figure 2 and Figure 3, and
3. Modify the Makefile as indicated in Figure 4 and make drstran.

2.7.6.3 Source code and Makefile changes

When adding a C input routine, it is necessary to modify the routine **dtreadc.c** to call the new routine. **dtreadc.c** is a generic read routine for all C input routines. It’s function is to test the input format and call the appropriate input routine for that format. Figure 2 illustrates the changes needed to add a new C routine.

FIGURE 2 dtreadc.c

```
*****
Routine: int dtreadc(slab,file,data)
-----

Description:
-----
Read the data described by 'slab', from input file 'file',
into array 'data'. (C version)

Arguments: (=: input; := output; ==: both)
-----
slab      := handle for structure describing the variable to read.
file      := handle for structure describing the input file.
data      := returned data

Function Returns:
-----
0: success
nonzero: failure
*****/
#include <stdio.h>
#include "dtinterc.h"
extern int dtreadAscii();
extern int dtreadBin();
extern int new-input-routine();
int
dtreadc(slab,file,data)
void *slab,*file,*data;
{
    char *format;
    format=GetFileFormat(file);
    if (!strcmp(format,"ASCII"))
        return dtreadAscii(slab,file,data);
```

```

else if (!strcmp(format,"BIN"))
    return dtreadBin(slab,file,data);
else if (!strcmp(format,"new-format-identifier"))
    return new-input-routine(slab,file,data);
else
    printf("C format not recognized: %s.\n",format);
return 1;
}

```

Similarly, when adding a Fortran input routine, it is necessary to change the routine dtreadf.F. Figure 3 illustrates the necessary modifications:

FIGURE 3 dtreadf.F

```

C*****
C
C Routine:
C -----
C integer function dtreadf(slab,file,data)
C integer slab,file,data(*)
C
C Description:
C -----
C Read data specified in structure 'slab', from file 'file'
C into data array 'data'. (Fortran version)
C
C Arguments: (=: input; := output; == both)
C -----
C slab      := handle for structure describing the variable to read.
C file      := handle for structure describing the input file.
C data      := returned data
C
C Function Returns:
C -----
C 0: success
C nonzero: failure
C*****

#include "dtinterf.h"
character*256 formatid
integer dtreadFbin,dtreadUTF,new-input-routine

call GetFileFormat(file,formatid)
if(formatid(1:4).eq.'FBIN') then
    dtreadf=dtreadFbin(slab,file,data)
    return
elseif(formatid(1:3).eq.'UTF') then
    dtreadf=dtreadUTF(slab,file,data)
    return
elseif(formatid(1:character-length-of-new-identifier).eq.'new-format-identifier') then
    new-input-routine(slab,file,data)
    return
else
    print '("Fortran format not recognized: ",A,".")',formatid

```

```

        dtreadf=1
    endif

    return
end

```

Figure 4 illustrates the necessary changes in the Makefile:

FIGURE 4 Sample Makefile for drstran

```

# drstran Makefile
#
# make drstran

# CCROOTDIR is typically /usr/CC/sun4 or /usr2/CC/sun4
# DRSLIB is the directory containing the DRS library libdrs.a
# FORTDIR is the directory containing the f77 libraries

CCLIB= $(CCROOTDIR)           # C++ libraries
DRSLIB      = /usr/local/drs # DRS libraries and includes
DRSINC= $(DRSLIB)
DRSTRANINC  = .               # drstran includes
FORTDIR     = /usr/lang/SC1.0 # f77 directory

READF=dtreadf.F readFbin.F readUTF.F new-Fortran-routines
READC=dtreadc.c readAscii.c readBin.c new-C-routines
READCC=dtreadcc.c readDrs.c

INCLUDE = -I$(CCLIB)/incl -I$(DRSINC) -I$(DRSTRANINC)
LOADDIR=-L$(CCLIB) -L$(DRSLIB) -L$(FORTDIR) -L$(CCLIB) -L$(DRSTRANINC)
DEBUG=-O
CFLAGS = $(INCLUDE)
FFLAGS = -e $(INCLUDE) $(DEBUG)
LDFLAGS=
LOADLIBS = -ldrstran -ll -ldrsc -lstrings -ldrsc -ldrs -lF77 -lc -lm -lc

OMAIN = header.o main.o
CSRCS = $(READC)
FSRCS = $(READF)

OREADC = $(READC:.c=.o)
OREADF = $(READF:.F=.o)
OREADCC = $(READCC:.c=.o)
GOAL = drstran

#-----
$(GOAL): $(OMAIN) $(OREADF) $(OREADC) $(OREADCC)
        $(CC) $(CFLAGS) -O $(LDFLAGS) -o $@ $(OMAIN) $(OREADF) $(OREADC) $(OREADCC)
        $(LOADDIR) $(LOADLIBS)

$(OREADF): $(READF)

```

```
$(COMPILE.F) $< -o $@  
$(OREADC): $(READC)  
    $(COMPILE.c) -O $< -o $@  
$(OREADC): $(READCC)  
    $(COMPILE.c) -g $< -o $@
```

Sample Input Routines and metafiles

A.1 readBin.c

```
/******  
  
Routine: int dtreadBin(slab,file,data)  
-----  
  
Description:  
-----  
Read the data described by 'slab', from input file 'file',  
into array 'data'.  
  
Arguments: (=: input; := output; := both)  
-----  
slab      =: handle for structure describing the variable to read.  
file      =: handle for structure describing the input file.  
data      := returned data  
  
Function Returns:  
-----  
0: success  
nonzero: failure
```

```

*****/
#include <stdio.h>
#include "dtinterc.h"
int
dtreadBin(slab,file,data)
void *slab,*file;
float *data;
{
    char *format,*path;
    int i,nelements,c,nread;
    FILE *fp;
    double *missingDataFlag;
    float fmissing;

    format=GetFileFormat(file);
    if(strcmp(format,"BIN")){
        printf("Invalid format: %s, should be BIN.\n",format);
        return 1;
    }
    path=GetFilePath(file);
    if(!(fp=GetFileFp(file))){
        if((fp=fopen(path,"r"))==NULL){
            printf("Error opening file %s.\n",path);
            return 1;
        }
        SetFileFp(file,fp);
    }

    nelements=GetSlabNelements(slab);
    if((nread=fread(data,sizeof *data,nelements,fp)<nelements){
        printf("Only read %d items from %s, expected %d.\n",
            nread,path,nelements);
        return 1;
    }
    if(GetNthEscapeInt(1) && (missingDataFlag=GetNthEscapeReal(1)) &&
        (*missingDataFlag != 1.0e20)){
        fmissing = *missingDataFlag;
        for(i=0;i<nelements; i++,data++)
            if(*data == fmissing) *data=1.0e20;
    }

    return 0;
}

```

A.2 readFbin.F

```

C*****
c
c Routine:
c -----
c integer function dtreadFbin(slab,file,databuf)
c integer slab,file
c
c Description:
c -----
c Read data specified in structure 'slab', from file 'file'
c into data array 'data'.

```

```

c
c   Arguments: (=: input; := output; :=: both)
c   -----
c   slab      := handle for structure describing the variable to read.
c   file      := handle for structure describing the input file.
c   databuf  := returned data
c
c   Function Returns:
c   -----
c       0: success
c   nonzero: failure
c
c*****
#include "dtinterf.h"
    parameter(lun=7)
    real databuf(*)
    character*256 formatid
    character*1024 path
    integer getdata

    dtreadFbin=0

    call GetFileFormat(file,formatid)
    if(formatid(1:4).ne.'FBIN') then
        print '("Invalid format: ",A," should be FBIN.")',formatid
        dtreadFbin=1
        return
    endif

    call GetFilePath(file,path)
    if(GetFileLun(file).eq.0) then
        open(unit=lun,file=path,
$         form='unformatted',status='old',err=9001)
        call SetFileLun(file,lun)
    endif

    nelements = GetSlabNelements(slab)
    dtreadFbin= getdata(databuf,nelements,path)
    go to 9000
9001 continue
    print '("Error opening ",A)',path
    dtreadFbin=1
    go to 9000
9000 continue
    return
end

    integer function getdata(databuf,nelems,path)
#include "dtinterf.h"
    parameter(lun=7)
    real databuf(nelems)
    integer nelems,iform,i
    character*1024 path

    getdata=0

    read(lun,err=9002) databuf
    if(GetNthEscapeInt(1,iform)) go to 9000

```

```

        if(iform.eq.1) then
            if(GetNthEscapeReal(1,xmissing)) go to 9004
            if(xmissing.eq.1.0e20) go to 9000
            do 100 i=1,nelems
                if(databuf(i).eq.xmissing) databuf(i)=1.0e20
100         continue
            endif
            go to 9000
9002        continue
            print '("Error reading ",A)',path
            getdata=1
            go to 9000
9004        continue
            print '("No missing value specified in escape section of metafile")'
            getdata=1
            go to 9000
9000        continue
            return
        end

```

A.3 readDrs.C

Although this manual does not describe the process of adding input routines written in C++, for completeness a sample C++ input routine is illustrated here.

```

/*****

Routine: int dtreadDrs(DrsSlab *slab,DtFile *file,void *data)
-----

Description:
-----
Read the data described by 'slab', from input file 'file',
into array 'data'.

Arguments: (:= input; := output; := both)
-----
slab      := handle for structure describing the variable to read.
file      := handle for structure describing the input file.
data      := returned data

Function Returns:
-----
0: success
nonzero: failure

*****/
#include "drstran.h"
int
dtreadDrs(DrsSlab *slab,DtFile *file,void *data)
{
DrsVariable *fv;

if(strcmp(file->format->ID,"DRSINPUT"))
dtError("Wrong format in read routine: %s.\n",file->format->ID);

file->openReadOnly(7,8);
data=slab->read(*(DrsFile *)file);

```

```
/* Set source,title,units from file if equal to %% in metafile */
fv=file->lookup(slab->variable->name);
if(!strcmp(slab->variable->comments,"%%"))
(void) SetSlabSource(slab,fv->comments);
if(!strcmp(slab->variable->title,"%%"))
(void) SetSlabTitle(slab,fv->title);
if(!strcmp(slab->variable->units,"%%"))
(void) SetSlabUnits(slab,fv->units);

file->close();
return data==(void *)0;
}
```

B.1 bin.met

```
/* Usage: drstran [cpp options] -DIN=<Input binary file> -DOUT=<Output DRS filename (no extension)>
bin.met

Metafile for translating unformatted (non-Fortran-generated) binary, rectangular array(s) to DRS
*/
#include "formats.met"
#include "domains.met"

Inputfiles = {
{IN,BIN}
}

Domains = {
{DOM,{T21_ECMWF}}
}

Variables = {
{evapsfc,DOM,units="mm/day",float,OUT,title="Evaporation at the Surface",source="means jun 01-0*"}
{hflxsen,DOM,units="W/m^2",float,OUT,title="Sensible Heat Flux",source="means jun 01-0*"}
{prtot,DOM,units="mm/day",float,OUT,title="Total Precipitation",source="means jun 01-0*"}
}

FileVariables = {
```

```

{{evapsfc,hflxsen,prtot},IN}
}
/* If missing data is to be translated, add or replace the following line with:

Escape = {1,<missing-data-value>}

For example,

Escape = {1,-99.9}

will cause all values -99.9 to be translated to the DRS missing value (1.0e20).
If there is no missing data, or it is not to be translated, the line may be
omitted.
*/
//Escape = {1,-999.9}

```

B.2 ASCII.met

```

/* Usage: drstran [cpp options] -DIN=<input file> -DOUT=<output file> <this file>

Metafile for translating file consisting of blank-separated, ASCII values into DRS format.

For example:
To translate file 'abc' to DRS file 'xyz.dat', type

drstran -DIN=abc -DOUT=xyz ascii.met

*/
/*-----*/

#include "formats.met"
#include "domains.met"

Inputfiles = {
{IN,ASCII}
}

Domains = {
{DOM,{T21_ECMWF}}
}

Variables = {
{evapsfc,DOM,units="mm/day",float,OUT,title="Evaporation at the Surface",source="means jun 01-0*"}
{hflxsen,DOM,units="W/m^2",float,OUT,title="Sensible Heat Flux",source="means jun 01-0*"}
{prtot,DOM,units="mm/day",float,OUT,title="Total Precipitation",source="means jun 01-0*"}
}

FileVariables = {
{{evapsfc,hflxsen,prtot},IN}
}

Escape={
-9999.0 /* Missing data value */
}

```

B.3 domains.met

```
/*
  This is the domain dictionary for translating DRS files.
*/

Dimensions = {
  {CCM40LAT,values={ /* CCM Gaussian latitudes for 48x40 grid */
    86.60, 82.19, 77.76, 73.32, 68.88, 64.44, 59.99, 55.55, 51.11, 46.66,
    42.22, 37.77, 33.33, 28.89, 24.44, 20.00, 15.55, 11.11, 6.67, 2.22,
    -2.22, -6.67, -11.11, -15.55, -20.00, -24.44, -28.89, -33.33, -37.77, -42.22,
    -46.66, -51.11, -55.55, -59.99, -64.44, -68.88, -73.32, -77.76, -82.19, -86.60},
    name=Latitude, units=Degrees}
  {CCM48LON, evenValues={0.0,360.0,48}, name=Longitude, units=degrees}
  {T21_LON,evenValues={0.0,360.0,64},name=longitude,units=degrees}
  {T21_GAUSS_LAT,values={
    85.76058, 80.26878, 74.74454, 69.21297, 63.67863, 58.14295,
    52.60653, 47.06964, 41.53246, 35.99508, 30.45755, 24.91993,
    19.38223, 13.84448, 8.306703, 2.768903, -2.768903, -8.306703,
    -13.84448, -19.38223, -24.91993, -30.45755, -35.99508, -41.53246,
    -47.06964, -52.60653, -58.14295, -63.67863, -69.21297, -74.74454,
    -80.26878, -85.76058}, name=latitude,units=degrees}
  {T42_LON,evenValues={0.0,360.0,128}, name=Longitude, units=degrees}
  {T42_GAUSS_LAT,values={
    87.86379, 85.09652, 82.31291, 79.5256, 76.73689, 73.94751,
    71.15775, 68.36775, 65.57761, 62.78735, 59.99702, 57.20663,
    54.4162, 51.62573, 48.83524, 46.04472, 43.25419, 40.46365,
    37.67309, 34.88252, 32.09194, 29.30136, 26.51077, 23.72017,
    20.92957, 18.13897, 15.34836, 12.55776, 9.767145, 6.976533,
    4.18592, 1.395307, -1.395307, -4.18592, -6.976533, -9.767145,
    -12.55776, -15.34836, -18.13897, -20.92957, -23.72017, -26.51077,
    -29.30136, -32.09194, -34.88252, -37.67309, -40.46365, -43.25419,
    -46.04472, -48.83524, -51.62573, -54.4162, -57.20663, -59.99702,
    -62.78735, -65.57761, -68.36775, -71.15775, -73.94751, -76.73689,
    -79.5256, -82.31291, -85.09652, -87.86379},
    name=latitude,units=degrees}
  {T63_LON,evenValues={0.0,360.0,192},name=longitude,units=degrees}
  {T63_GAUSS_LAT,values={
    88.57217, 86.72253, 84.86197, 82.99894, 81.13497, 79.27055,
    77.40588, 75.54106, 73.67613, 71.81113, 69.94608, 68.08099,
    66.21587, 64.35072, 62.48557, 60.6204, 58.75521, 56.89001,
    55.02481, 53.15959, 51.29438, 49.42915, 47.56392, 45.69869,
    43.83346, 41.96822, 40.10298, 38.23774, 36.37249, 34.50724,
    32.64199, 30.77674, 28.91149, 27.04624, 25.18098, 23.31573,
    21.45047, 19.58522, 17.71996, 15.8547, 13.98945, 12.12419,
    10.25893, 8.393668, 6.528409, 4.663149, 2.79789, .9326299,
    -.9326299, -2.79789, -4.663149, -6.528409, -8.393668, -10.25893,
    -12.12419, -13.98945, -15.8547, -17.71996, -19.58522, -21.45047,
    -23.31573, -25.18098, -27.04624, -28.91149, -30.77674, -32.64199,
    -34.50724, -36.37249, -38.23774, -40.10298, -41.96822, -43.83346,
    -45.69869, -47.56392, -49.42915, -51.29438, -53.15959, -55.02481,
    -56.89001, -58.75521, -60.6204, -62.48557, -64.35072, -66.21587,
    -68.08099, -69.94608, -71.81113, -73.67613, -75.54106, -77.40588,
    -79.27055, -81.13497, -82.99894, -84.86197, -86.72253, -88.57217},
    name=latitude,units=degrees}
  {T106_LON,evenValues={0.0,360.0,320},name=longitude,units=degrees}
```

```

{T106_GAUSS_LAT,values={
  89.14152, 88.02943, 86.91077, 85.79063, 84.66992, 83.54894,
  82.42781, 81.30659, 80.1853, 79.06398, 77.94262, 76.82124,
  75.69984, 74.57843, 73.457, 72.33557, 71.21413, 70.09269,
  68.97124, 67.84978, 66.72832, 65.60686, 64.4854, 63.36393,
  62.24246, 61.12099, 59.99952, 58.87804, 57.75657, 56.63509,
  55.51361, 54.39213, 53.27065, 52.14917, 51.02769, 49.90621,
  48.78473, 47.66325, 46.54176, 45.42028, 44.29879, 43.17731,
  42.05582, 40.93434, 39.81285, 38.69136, 37.56988, 36.44839,
  35.3269, 34.20542, 33.08393, 31.96244, 30.84095, 29.71947,
  28.59798, 27.47649, 26.355, 25.23351, 24.11202, 22.99054,
  21.86905, 20.74756, 19.62607, 18.50458, 17.38309, 16.2616,
  15.14011, 14.01862, 12.89713, 11.77564, 10.65415, 9.532663,
  8.411174, 7.289684, 6.168194, 5.046704, 3.925215, 2.803725,
  1.682235, .5607449, -.5607449, -1.682235, -2.803725, -3.925215,
  -5.046704, -6.168194, -7.289684, -8.411174, -9.532663, -10.65415,
  -11.77564, -12.89713, -14.01862, -15.14011, -16.2616, -17.38309,
  -18.50458, -19.62607, -20.74756, -21.86905, -22.99054, -24.11202,
  -25.23351, -26.355, -27.47649, -28.59798, -29.71947, -30.84095,
  -31.96244, -33.08393, -34.20542, -35.3269, -36.44839, -37.56988,
  -38.69136, -39.81285, -40.93434, -42.05582, -43.17731, -44.29879,
  -45.42028, -46.54176, -47.66325, -48.78473, -49.90621, -51.02769,
  -52.14917, -53.27065, -54.39213, -55.51361, -56.63509, -57.75657,
  -58.87804, -59.99952, -61.12099, -62.24246, -63.36393, -64.4854,
  -65.60686, -66.72832, -67.84978, -68.97124, -70.09269, -71.21413,
  -72.33557, -73.457, -74.57843, -75.69984, -76.82124, -77.94262,
  -79.06398, -80.1853, -81.30659, -82.42781, -83.54894, -84.66992,
  -85.79063, -86.91077, -88.02943, -89.14152
},name=latitude,units=degrees}
{JAN,values={1}}
{FEB,values={2}}
{MAR,values={3}}
{APR,values={4}}
{MAY,values={5}}
{JUN,values={6}}
{JUL,values={7}}
{AUG,values={8}}
{SEP,values={9}}
{OCT,values={10}}
{NOV,values={11}}
{DEC,values={12}}
}

Domains = {
{CCM40X48, {CCM40LAT, CCM48LON}}
{T21_ECMWF, {T21_LON, T21_GAUSS_LAT}}
{T42_ECMWF, {T42_LON, T42_GAUSS_LAT}}
{T63_ECMWF, {T63_LON, T63_GAUSS_LAT}}
{T106_ECMWF, {T106_LON, T106_GAUSS_LAT}}
}

```

DRS Dictionary File Structure

With each DRS data (.dat) file, DRS associates a dictionary (.dic) file. This section describes the structure of a DRS dictionary file.

A DRS dictionary file consists of a sequence of 512-byte records. The first record is a header record. Following the header record are two records for each variable in the data file. Consequently, if the data file contains *ivar* variables, the dictionary file will contain $(2*ivar) + 1$ records, of 512 bytes each.

Table 15 describes the structure of the header record:

TABLE 15

DRS dictionary file header record

Byte (octal)	Type	Elements	Description
0	C40	1	Data file name (V2.0 and previous; not used in V2.1)
50	I4	1	Number of variables
54	I4	1	Number of bytes in the data file
60	C8	1	File tag (= 'DRS_DICT')

70	F4	1	DRS version number
74	-	-	Reserved

Following the header record, the dictionary file contains two 512-byte records for each variable in the data file. Table 16 and Table 17 describe the structure of each record type:

TABLE 16

DRS dictionary file variable record type I

Byte (octal)	Type	Elements	Description
0	C120	1	Variable source comments
170	C16	1	Variable name
210	C80	1	Variable title
330	C40	1	Variable units
400	C8	1	Date written (MM/DD/YY)
410	C8	1	Time written (HH:MM:SS)
420	C8	1	Variable datatype ('R*4' 'R*8' 'I*4' 'I*8' 'C*n')
430	C16	4	Dimension name, for each dimension. For dimension variables written with PUTVDIM, the first name is set to 'internal', the remaining values are blank;
530	C40	4	Dimension units, for each dimension. For dimension variables written with PUTVDIM, the first name is set to 'internal', the remaining values are blank;
770	-	-	Reserved

TABLE 17

DRS dictionary file variable record type II

Byte (octal)	Type	Elements	Description
0	I4	1	Number of instances (1 or 2)
4	I4	1	Number of dimensions
10	I4	1	Number of elements
14	I4	1	Number of bytes per element
20	I4	8	Dimension length (instance,dimension)
60	F4	8	Dimension first element (instance,dimension); if the dimension is unevenly-spaced, this is set to 1.0
120	F4	8	Dimension last element (instance,dimension); if the dimension is unevenly-spaced, this is set to the floating-point equivalent of the length of the dimension.
160	I4	4	Distance, in bytes between successive elements of the dimension, for each dimension

200	I4	1	1-origin byte address of the first element of the variable in the data file
204	I4	4	Dimension type, for each dimension; 1 = evenly-spaced, 2 = unevenly-spaced
224	I4	4	Record number of the associated dimension variable, if the dimension is unevenly-spaced, or -1 if the dimension is evenly-spaced, for each dimension
244	I4	4	Dimension monotonicity, if the dimension is evenly-spaced; 1 = increasing, -1 = decreasing, 0 = unevenly-spaced; for each dimension
264	F4	1	First data value, for dimension variables only
270	F4	1	Last data value, for dimension variables only
274	F4	4	Actual first value of the dimension, if the dimension is unevenly-spaced, for each dimension
314	F4	4	Actual last value of the dimension, if the dimension is unevenly-spaced, for each dimension
334	-	-	Reserved

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